

MANAGEMENT OF CONGESTED CLASSROOMS IN BASIC EDUCATION SCHOOLS IN SOKOTO METROPOLIS: THE TEACHERS' EXPERIENCE

By

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Abstract

The paper examines teachers' struggles to manage teaching and learning in highly congested classrooms in some selected basic schools in Sokoto metropolis. It is observed that within the metropolis, many basic schools are now facing a challenge of congestion of students in the classrooms. As a result of this, teachers find it extremely difficult to deliver as effectively as possible. Therefore, a study of this nature which seeks to address the problems of students' congestion in the classroom is not only needed but also necessary. Qualitative research method of data collection was used in the study. The method accommodates the usage of population samples of students, teachers, number of schools and research questions within the study area. The study in the final analysis describes government's inability to provide the needed classrooms in the schools as one of the major factors responsible for classroom congestion in the schools which negatively affect teachers' performance. At the same time it demonstrates a pedagogical approach to handle such situation.

Introduction

The concern of every professional teacher, not only in the Sokoto metropolis, but also throughout the world is to deliver effectively in his/her classroom teaching. Therefore, the provision of conducive learning environment in the school by the government is necessary. But, unfortunately, the reverse is the case because government fails to provide the needful which will go a long to address the challenge of classroom congestion. This attitude by the government adversely affects teachers' performance

in school. In spite of the above factors, teachers must be able to maintain order and have full control of their classrooms. Class size and Pupil-Teacher Ratio (PTR) are class factors that influence classroom control, in other word maintenance of order and proper use of space by teachers. Large class size, high Pupil-Teacher Ratio (PTR) and congested classrooms are found by many researches to be of negative effect to effective teaching and learning. Majanga, (2011 p 46,) found out that large class, high pupil-teacher ratio and congested classrooms are factors that normally affect classroom interaction, because

according to him, teachers find it difficult to give personalized attention to all the pupils, give adequate assignment to test what have been taught and take full control of their classes.

It is against this background that the paper examined teachers' struggles in handling congested classrooms at basic education level in Sokoto metropolis.

Conceptual Framework

Concept of Class-Size: Kariuki and Guantai (2005) maintained that class-size has been an important issue in discussion and dialogue on quality of education, as well as issue of financing education especially teacher numbers and remuneration. As a result class-size has not only been one of the most research

topics in education but also a sensitive and almost politically emotional issues in many countries. In Africa as many countries introduce and implement universal basic education, within the context of scarce resources and hence low capacity to employ adequate teachers, class-size is a major challenge for ministries of education and finance. The quest for the optimal class size remains a big challenge in balancing the pressure for improved quality which is believed to be linked with small size and fiscal constraints and conditionality that prevail in countries with heavy donor support in financing education especially primary education. In view of this it is imperative therefore to know what this class size is all about.

Table 1: Minimum class sizes according to different scholars

Author	Minimum size of large class
Berker (1976)	55
Chimombo (1986)	50
Dixon (1986)	40
Finocchiarol (1989)	65
George (1991)	60
Hayes (1997)	50
Holiday (1996)	50
Hubbard et al (1983)	45
Li (1977)	50
Long (1977)	60
Nolasco&Artur (1986)	40

Source: Education for All (EFA), 2015.

Concept of Overcrowded classroom

A classroom is said to be overcrowded in which the number of students exceeds the optimum level such that it causes hindrance in the teaching and learning process (Tayeg, 2015) Researchers argue that there is no exact definition of large class. It differs from country to country and from one situation of teaching to another. Hayes (1997) states that there can be no quantitative definition of what constitute overcrowded class, as perception of this will vary from context to context. Dror (1996) sees that large is of course a relation term and what large class is, will vary from place to place. A group of twenty may be considered large; in my own teaching situation 40-50. A study done by a team of the Lancaster Leads Language Learning in large class research project (project report No. 4) of Coleman et al, indicates the average perception of the large class may be around 50 students (p 302). For example some people hold that 50 would be large enough for a class; others would argue that a large class could have as many as over 100 or over 150 students.

Concept of Classroom management

Classroom Management is described as the teacher's ability to co-operatively manage time, space, resources and student's roles and behaviour to provide a climate that encourages learning. (Robert and Jana, 2003 in Atanda, A. I

and Jaiyeoba, A. O, 2011). There are immediate procedures within the classroom which teachers can implement as management strategy. One of such procedures is attending to physical settings of the classroom which include proper arrangement of the classroom seats and desks. In other words, classroom management is defined as creating and maintaining a learning environment that support instructions and support students' achievements. Akuebue (1999) conceptualizes classroom management as action that are intended to create favourable conditions that will facilitate instructions and actions that are aimed at regulating the social behavior of the pupils. Moreover, in his definition of classroom management, Atanda (2009) said it involves the utilization of material resources and securing the co-operation of students for performing the function of planning, organizing, directing and coordinating at classroom level by teachers.

Theoretical Framework

Symbolic interactionist reflects the micro sociological perspective and was largely influenced by the work of early sociologist and philosophers, such as George Simmel, Charles Cooley, George Herbert Mead and Erving Goffman. Symbolic interactionism emphasized that human behaviour is influenced by definitions and meanings that are created and maintained through symbolic

interactions with others. Symbolic interaction also suggests that our identity or sense of self is shaped by social interaction. We develop our self-concept by observing how others interact with us and label us. By observing how others view us, we see a reflection of ourselves that Cooley calls the “looking glass self” (Mooney, Knox and Schacht, 2007). This theory is relevant to this study because it is the theory that deals with micro level of analysis. Meaning of action is understood within the context of interaction.

Methodology

The population of this study comprises twenty two(22) primary schools, six hundred and eighty eight(688) teachers, three hundred and forty four (344)classrooms and forty one thousand and ten(41010) pupils/students. Twenty (20) junior secondary schools, three hundred and ten (310) teachers, one hundred and thirty nine (139) classrooms and eleven thousand nine hundred and seventy nine (11, 979) number of pupils/students. Purposive sampling was used to select the five (5) Basic Education schools for the study. While convenience sampling technique was used in selecting the forty five (45) classroom, Forty five (45) Teachers and for the study. Structured interview was the instrument used for data collection, and content analysis was used in analyzing data collected via the structured interview

Data Analysis and Presentation.

A vast majority of the respondents responded that they use talk (frequent verbal command or directives) like hey! Listen! Keep quiet! Stop that! and host of other verbal directives in their effort to maintain order during lesson. This opinion is held by the following respondents (R3, R4, R6, R7, R8, R9, R11, R12, R13, R14, R15, R15, R16, R17, R18, R19, R20, R21, R23, R26, R29, R30, R31, R32, R33, R40, R41, R42, R43, R44, \$ R45). One of these respondents said; he used to remind them about his rules and regulations, before the commencement of the lesson, and he keeps talking to them to make sure that they cooperate and listen attentively as lesson proceeded (R29). The implication of this strategy is that teachers will be spending most of their lesson time on frequent talking, shouting and other verbal directives in their struggle to put their classes in order at the expense of the actual work of teaching.

Second category of respondents under this theme opined that they use the strategy of threat or coercion to enforce their definition of order on their pupils during lesson. This strategy involves writing names of noisemakers, using cane or frowning of face to create fear in the mind of their pupils so that they will not find it easy to misbehave during lesson. Respondent that hold this view are (R1, R5, R7, R8, R10, R12, R35, R33, \$ R34).One of these respondents said; he used cane to threaten his pupils if they made noise, and they listen for fear of being flogged. Sometimes he frowned his face during lesson so that his

pupils would not find it easy to misbehave while lesson is ongoing. (R5) The implication of this strategy is that, by doing this, teachers are only creating fear in the minds of their pupils, thereby forcing them to listen instead of motivating them and arousing their interest in the lesson. Their seeming concentration therefore will be out of fear of being punished and not for the sake of learning.

Third category of respondents under this theme responded that they use measures like play, forced sleep, asking of pupils to stand up, sit down, hands up, and so on. These measures according to them help them to establish their definition of order thereby making pupils to concentrate on the lesson. Respondents with this view are (R7, R41, R11, R17, \$ R20). One of these respondents said; he use to assign the class monitor to write down names of those making noise while lesson is ongoing, and they keep silence for fear of being included among those making noise. (R20).

The fourth category of the respondents under this theme opined that they use the strategy of assigning assistant teacher who is responsible for controlling the pupils and making sure that they listen and concentrate on the lesson while the teacher proceed with the task of teaching. Respondents with this view are (R40 \$ R41). One of these respondents said: "Like you can see one teacher cannot be able to manage this kind of class, because of the congestion, two teachers does the work at a time by

complementing each other, one will teach while the other will control the pupils" (R41). The implication of this strategy is that, the scenario will lead to a situation whereby the attention of pupils will be divided between the teacher trying to control them and the teacher doing the work of teaching as such the rate of their concentration and the amount of learning will be diversely affected.

How Teachers Evaluate Their Lesson in Congested Classroom.

A vast majority of the respondents under this theme responded that they ask questions during and after lesson in their effort to evaluate their pupils. Respondents that hold this view are (R1, R3, R4, R10, R11, R12, R9, R9, R13, R14, R17, R16, R18, R19, R20, R21, R22, R23, R24, R15, R26, R27, R28, R29, R30, R31, R32, R33, R34, R35, R36, R37, R38, R39, R40, R41, R42, \$ R43).One of these respondents said; he used to ask them one after the other if majority of them responded positively, he has achieved his objective of the lesson (R42)

Another respondent said; he evaluates his pupils by demanding them to ask questions and if they refuse then he asks them. If three (3) pupils responded positively he achieves his objective of my lesson. (R22). Another respondent said; he evaluates his lesson by asking questions and observing the number of pupils that raised up their hands. Based on that, he concludes whether they have

understood or otherwise (R29). Second category of respondents under this theme responded that they evaluate their pupils by giving them class work, homework, or assignment. Respondents with this view are (R5, R30, R41, R11, \$ R15). The third category of respondents under this theme deviate from answering this question which suggest to me that they either didn't understand the question or they don't use to evaluate their pupils perhaps due to congestion in their classrooms.

How Teachers Carry Their Pupils Along in Congested Classroom During Lesson (learner-centered)

Majority of respondents under this theme responded that they carry their pupils along during lesson by throwing questions frequently to them as lessons proceed. This according to them will enable pupils to contribute to the progress as well as the success of the lesson. Respondents with this view are (R1, R2, R4, R5, R7, R9, R10, R11, R12, R13, R15, R17, R18, R19, R20, R21, R22, R23, R25, R27, R29, R30, R31 \$ R32). Second category of respondents under this theme opined that they carry their pupils along during lesson by reading, discussing, and explaining the lesson with them. Respondents with this view are (R3, R33, R34, R35, R36, R40, R41, \$ R43). One of these respondents said; he use to ask them if they have an idea about the topic of the day at the beginning of the lesson. He also tells them that he will award marks based on their contribution to the lesson. This

encourages them to contribute to the success of the lesson (R35)

Third category of respondents under this theme responded that they carry their pupils along during lesson by being friendly with them, this according to them make them feel free and fully partake in the lesson. Respondents with this view are (R11 \$ R40). Fourth category of respondents under this theme responded that they use both English and Hausa during lesson for better understanding of their pupils. One of these respondents said; he always sings a song to his pupils at the beginning of the lesson in order to arouse their interest and attention towards his lesson (R11).

Fifth category of respondents under this theme gives a vague response to this question which suggests to me that they didn't understand the question .The respondents are, (R44, R45, R30, R12, R15, \$ R41). One of these respondents said; he carries his pupils, along during lesson by making a good evaluation (R17). But he fails to elaborate on what he means by proper evaluation. Sixth categories of respondents under this theme deviate from answering this question perhaps they have not understood the question. Respondents under this category are (R13, and R20).

Comfort ability or Otherwise of Teaching in Overcrowded Classroom

Majority of the respondents under this theme responded that they are not comfortable when teaching in congested

classroom especially during the hot season. Respondents with this view are (R1, R2, R3, R4, R5, R7, R8, R9, R10, R12, R13, R14, R15, R16, R17, R19, R20, R22, R23, R25, R27, R30, R32, R42, R33, R34, R35 & R36). One of these respondents said; he experiences headache every day, because of this congestion, one is in fear of matching their legs or falling on the floor when trying to pass through them to address a problem sighted at the back (R34) Another category of respondents under this theme responded that they are comfortable when teaching in overcrowded classroom. Most of them they are comfortable, because they are used to the situation. Respondents with this view are (R6, R11, R18, R21, R24, R26, R28, R29, R31, R32, R37, R38, R39, R40, R41, R42, R43, R44, & R45). One of these respondents said; he has taught in overcrowded classrooms for over thirteen (13) years; the congestion is even less now compared to some years back (R42) another respondent said; at first, he was threatened by their number, but now that he is used to the situation and has become comfortable to some extent (R11).

How Teachers Motivate Their Pupils to Learn During Lesson in Congested Classrooms.

Majority of the respondents under this theme responded that they motivate pupils by advising to reflect on the relevance and importance of education to their lives and the society at large. This is done in order to boost their morale to

concentrate on the lesson. Respondents with this view are (R1, R2, R3, R4, R5, R7, R8, R9, R10, R11, R12, R13, R14, R15, R16, R17, R18, R20, R21, R22, R23, R24, R24, R25, & R25). One of these respondents said; he used to give them example with our political leaders like president, governors, ministers and so on. "I tell them that these political leaders get there, because they are educated; you too will be the future leaders of the society when you are educated" (R22). Second category of respondents under this theme responded that they motivate their pupils by the use of play, jokes, singing, smiling, clapping and even verbal remarks like good, very good, excellent and so on for pupils that give correct answers. Respondents with this view are (R26, R27, R28, R29, R30, R31, R32, R40, & R41). One of these respondents said: "They appreciate clapping, so I ask them to clap for any pupil that gives correct answer during my lesson. It actually motivates them. (R32). He personally observed that in one of the classes by constant and frequent clapping to the pupils that give correct answer, order, concentration and silence were established and maintained during the lesson. Third category of respondent under this theme responded that they motivate their pupils by giving them material gifts to appreciate their contribution to the lesson. Respondents with this view are (R14, R13, R23, R21, & R30). However, no teacher was observed giving any gift to any pupil to appreciate his or her contribution to the lesson.

Summary of the Major Findings

The major findings of the study are: The study revealed that, teachers in overcrowded classrooms apply a variety of strategies to enforce their definition of order on their pupils during lesson. Strategies such as the use of verbal commands and directives; use of threat/coercion, (flogging, shouting, writing of noise makers), moving round the classroom, and use of assistant teachers were some of the strategies employed by teachers to maintain order during lesson. A vast majority of the respondents evaluate their lesson by asking relevant questions during and after the lesson. While other respondents deviate from the question which suggests to the researcher that they either didn't understand the question or they do not use to evaluate their pupils perhaps due to congestion in their classrooms. Majority of respondents responded that they carry their pupils along during lesson by throwing questions frequently to them as lessons proceed and by reading, discussing, and explaining the lesson together with them. Majority of the respondents responded that they are not comfortable when teaching in congested classroom especially during the hot season. They would be eager to move out of the class because of the heat. Majority of the respondents responded that they motivate pupils by advising to reflect on the relevance and importance of education to their lives and the society at large. This is done in order to boost their morale to concentrate on the lesson

Conclusion

In an ideal classroom set up, teachers are comfortable while teaching; they move round the classroom freely; give personalized attention to their pupils, carry them along in the lesson; give them the required motivation; have proper classroom control; evaluate their lessons thoroughly and received proper feedback from the pupils. Whereas in a congested classroom the comfort ability is absolutely absent, so proper classroom control is not tenable. Teachers cannot give personalized attention to their pupils; they cannot evaluate and receive proper feedback from their pupils due to time constraint. Moreover the amount of teaching and learning activities in any congested classroom is small compared to the amount of distraction, noise making, mock fighting, bullying that dominate the lesson.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the following are hereby recommended: Teacher training institutions should endeavor to introduce courses capable of grooming and training the would-be teachers on how to properly handle highly congested classrooms. Government and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) also need to make adequate provision for training and re-training of teachers on how to handle contemporary pedagogical issues like classroom congestion. Teachers should endeavor to create a kind of classroom climate capable of arousing and

sustaining the interest and attention of their pupils by proper management of time, space, and other resources during lesson. Teachers should endeavour to make their teaching learner-centered by

applying the most suitable method of teaching that correspond with the nature of every lesson, no matter how rigorous it might appear to them.

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